

Santo Adriano: an Early Middle Ages territory

Interpretative visit

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Perambulations and the divisions of space in early medieval
Europe

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Plan

Today's plan is to visit a territory in central Asturias, the municipality of Santo Adriano, which is the present-day result of a medieval segmentation of the territory carried out by the monarchs of the Asturian kingdom in the ninth century. There are some documents that include perambulations to fix the boundaries of this territory, which was donated by the monarchs to a private monastery. The main problem for the historical study of these documents is that they are later copies, interpolated in the twelfth century. How much of them is authentic and how much is false is not an easy question to answer. Different scholars have tried to address this issue using two main methods: first, diplomatic analysis (Fernández Conde and Pedregal Montes, 1996) and, secondly, territorial analysis, such as the study of place names and their locations (Fernández Conde and Pedregal Montes, 1998; Fernández Fernández, 2012, 2017b; Muñiz López, 2012).

On the other hand, archaeologists have excavated and analyzed the Pre-Romanesque church of Santo Adriano de Tuñón (ninth century), an early medieval building that was part of the original donation (Adán Álvarez et al., 1991; Caballero Zoreda and Rodríguez Trobajo, 2010; Ríos González and Muñiz Álvarez, 2018). Other scholars have focused their archaeological work on peasant settlements mentioned in the monastic donation in order to evaluate the impact of the economic and social transformations introduced by these new early medieval centres of power (Fernández Fernández, 2012, 2017b).

To present this research our visit is organized in 3 main stops associated with their corresponding discussions:

1. The Pre-Romanesque church of Santo Adriano de Tuñón: the contributions of documentary analysis and archaeology of early medieval architecture.
2. La Cruz de Llinares: how the territory provides answers to solve the problems that documents imply.
3. Villanueva: the contribution of archaeological analysis of peasant settlements to understand the impact of early medieval centers of power.

1st Stop. The Pre-Romanesque Church of Santo Adriano

The construction of a royally promoted Pre-Romanesque church in a place called Tuñón is the starting point for the emergence of this new territory of Santo Adriano. According to the medieval documents, this church was founded by Alfonso III and his wife Jimena in 891, in the presence of the bishops of Coimbra, Iria Flavia, Astorga and Oviedo. The church was intended for a monastic community, probably pre-existing. Additionally, with the promotion of the new church and the donation of different properties, the monarchs were creating a new centre of power and territorial organization, a process very common in early medieval Europe, when the nobility and the monarchy promoted a number of privately owned monasteries. In other words, they were tools to support the monarchy's territorial action, reorganize settlements and centralize economic activity.

Despite these not being unusual actions in their historical context, there is an important debate about the authenticity of the documents that contain this information, because they were interpolated by Bishop Pelayo of Oviedo in the twelfth century. Thus, the question is: when the copy was made, how much text was added that was not in the original, and how much of the original was omitted? To address this problem, some scholars carried out a diplomatic analysis and an assessment of the texts, concluding that it is possible to identify, more or less, the original donation within the surviving copies (as there is more than one) (Fernández Conde and Pedregal Montes, 1996). Secondly, they conducted a territorial analysis by locating present-day place names that coincide with the medieval ones used in the text and tracing the boundaries of the perambulation associated with the donation (Fernández Conde and Pedregal

Montes, 1998). This work showed that the perambulation roughly coincides with the current boundaries of the municipality of Santo Adriano, demonstrating the ancient origins of this territorial structure. Thus, what exists today as Santo Adriano can be seen, from a territorial perspective, as the result of these actions.

In 1108, this bishop consecrated three altars dedicated to Saints Adrian and Natalia, St Peter and St Paul, and James, as recorded in an inscription preserved inside the church, which is transcribed below (García de Castro Valdés, 2008):

OVIEDO BISHOP PELAYO DEDICATED THIS CHURCH ON 11 AUGUST 1108. THE CENTRAL ALTAR, IN HONOUR OF THE SAINTS AND MARTYRS NATALIA AND ADRIAN; THE RIGHT, IN HONOUR OF THE HOLY APOSTLES PETER AND PAUL; THE LEFT, IN HONOUR OF THE APOSTLE JAMES. IN THE REIGN OF KING ALFONSO, SON OF KING FERNANDO, KING OF LEÓN AND TOLEDO, AND WITH DON EULALIO AS ABBOT OF THE SAME MONASTERY, WHO, AT THE TIME OF THE DEDICATION OF THE CHURCH, PLACED THREE NEW ALTAR STONES ABOVE THE THREE ALTARS...

The interpolation of the document and the consecration of the altars, both carried out by Bishop Pelayo, can be considered two synchronous and complementary actions intended to bring this small monastery and its possessions under the control of the Cathedral of Oviedo.

The church underwent major renovations throughout its history. The first coincided with the consecration in 1108; later ones took place in the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, and especially in the twentieth century (1949–1954), when there was a significant phase of restoration, whose most prominent figure was undoubtedly L. Menéndez Pidal, author of the last major works carried out on the church.

We will now briefly describe the architectural features of the temple. The church (Santo Adriano de Tuñón) has basilical distribution with three naves of three sections, separated by stone arches with keystones resting on brick pillars of rectangular section, made of masonry, covered with mortar, without impost or capital. The central nave is higher than the sides. It has three rectangular heads with two buttresses to the exterior and a front porch; a result of the reforms of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries. Originally it had a

tripartite Western forepart, with portico and two aisles and a central hall on the porch. The original temple walls are built of irregular limestone masonry, adorned with stones at the corners.

The naves were illuminated by 6 rectangular windows. The eastern wall of the church contains a mullioned window with two openings separated by a small central column. This window is the only access to the chamber above the apse. The three chapels are covered with barrel vaults and the naves with a wooden structure.

The sculptural decoration is reduced to a pair of columns of the triumphal arch of the central chapel with reused capitals of Roman tradition. In the sacristy there is a small piece of carved panel of gray marble with decorations which has parallels with others from San Miguel de Lillo, housed in the Archaeological Museum of Asturias.

The most important element of this building are the murals, located in the central chapel. Composed of concentric circles, vegetative elements, the sun and moon and a frieze of jagged triangular battlements, inspired in stiles from the south of the Iberian Peninsula. It also preserves some processional crosses.

These paintings are a mixture of different styles and influences, on the one hand motifs inherited from late antiquity and other styles that originate south of the Iberian Peninsula, possibly because of the participation of artisans who knew the Andalusian styles.

The belfry and main façade are the result of the reforms of the seventeenth and eighteenth century.

The excavations in the necropolis of the church have identified three phases of use. The first phase of burials (ninth-twelfth centuries) consists of slab graves oriented in relation to the apse. A second phase (twelfth-fifteenth centuries) includes both slab graves and pit burials oriented in an east-west direction, and a third phase of pit burials dating from the sixteenth-eighteenth centuries. There is no absolute radiocarbon dating; the proposed chronology is based on morphological parallels between tombs and associated archaeological materials (Adán Álvarez et al., 1991).

2nd Stop. The documents and the territory: perambulations and place names

Based on the copies of the original donation of Alfonso III and his wife Jimena at the end of the IX century we quote below the fragment where the text describe the boundaries of the new monastic domain. Although the text does not describe a perambulation in the strict sense, the precision of its topographical detail raises the possibility that such a ritual or juridical practice had already occurred, whether at the time of foundation, in the course of sacralization, or at another moment, as documented in some early medieval monastic contexts. Following Javier Fernández Conde and Amparo Pedregal documentary analysis this part is considered a true copy of the original donation (Fernández Conde and Pedregal Montes, 1996):

“Et concedimus ad memoriam eius uillas nostras et familias per terminis suis antiquas quod ad nos pertinet hodie die iuri nostro quieto, id est, inprimis, per illo riuulum qui descendit de Serande que dicunt Bulliera et per aqua uerto de coto de Pennin et per calellio de illa Uaca et per penna Aquilera et per Pena de Rege et per / (Fol. 2 v^o) illo traue et per busto Mezquini et per illo scuoio de Canpo et per arbore recobo et per illa cerca de illa Açorera et per Granda Rebolla et per illo scobio de porto et per bustello et per illa carrale antiqua que discurrit a Sancto Martino de Siones que es de domna Faquillo per illo termino de Sancto Martino usque in illo sabugo antiquo et directa linea per illa serra in infestum usque in ualles in termino de Sarrazino et per monte aluo et per fontem Recri et per illo scuoio ubi dicunt petra scripta ac fluuio et Trubia directaque linea per ipso fluuio usque in illo rego qui descurrit de Buanga et per

illo riulum in infestum usque in illa serra de Uerduzedo et per pando de Troncos et perilla (...) et per illo Asprone et per illo rego qui descurrit de Melandrinos qui dicunt Rio de la Froia usque in flumine Trubia ubi dicunt Pelago Nigro directa linea in infestum-per ipso flumine usque in illo que dicant Bullieya ubi prius diximus. Et feçimus et damus per istis terminus ab integritate cum familie uillas due in insis terminis sunt fundatas el commorantes...”

In the next table it is possible to correlate the early medieval place names and the current place names recovered by Javier Fernández Conde and Jesús Fernández (Fernández Conde and Pedregal Montes, 1998; Fernández Fernández, 2014).

G. Larragueta transcription	Current place name
per illo riulum qui descendit de Serande que dicunt Bulliera	Serrandi (aldea) y Buyera (field close to the Trubia river)
uerto de coto de Pennin	Copinín
Per penna de Rege	Peña Rei (mountain)
Per illo Trabe	Mountains
Per illo escouio de Campo	L'Escobiu del Campu
Per arbore recobo	Barricombu
Per illo scuio de Porto	Puertu (village)
Per bustello	Bustiello
Siones	Siones (village)
Sancto Martino	San Martín (deserted village)
Illo sabugo antiquo	El Sabugu
Per illa serra	La Sierra
ualles	Valles (deserted village)
monte aluo	Montovu (hamlet)
petra scripta	Peña La Escrita (mountain)
Buanga	Guanga (mountains and stream)
Pando de Troncos	Pandetroncos
Melandrinos	Melendrosu
Rio de la Froia	Riflor
Pelago Nigro	Plagón (Trubia River)

Once these place names are located within the territory, the boundary of the described area more or less coincides with that of the present-day municipality.

Fig. 2. The letter “T” indicate place names and stars indicate villages

In the following picture the place names from the document are located in the current landscape. Here, at our second stop, we can see the perambulation of the Santo Adriano territory as shown in the arrows below:

Fig. 4. Locations of early medieval territories and archaeological features

3rd Stop. San Romano, an early medieval village uncovered

The early medieval origin of the village:

In the donation dated to the ninth century, and in the part considered by Conde and Pedregal to be authentic, several villages are included. One of them is “uilla que dicunt Santi Romani iuxta fluuio Trubia”. This village is currently a neighbourhood of Villanueva, close to the Trubia River. The parish church is dedicated to San Romano, and the neighbourhood preserves its name.

The excavations carried out in this village since 2010 have confirmed the early medieval origin of the settlement (based on radiocarbon dates ranging from the seventh to the ninth centuries onwards) (Fernández Fernández, 2014, 2017a). This does not confirm the authenticity of the documents, but it does confirm that a settlement existed here at that time. Furthermore, the excavations indicate significant changes in the landscape and settlement during the tenth century, interpreted as an effect of monastic activity. We are therefore most likely dealing with one of the best-studied cases of the creation of an early medieval domain and of the analysis of its impact on the social and agrarian landscape.

The excavation of the open fields:

The focus of the excavations from 2015 to 2022 was an area of open field to the south of the present-day village, close to the medieval church. Approximately 30 cm of modern soil overlay layers of stony debris from a flash flood. The thickness of this layer varied across the village, and in the trench it reached a depth of approximately 80 cm. Towards the bottom of the flood debris, we recovered building stones and roof tiles from structures destroyed in the flood. Below the debris layer, we found a layer of medieval agricultural soil containing datable ceramics and fragments of animal bone.

The majority of the pottery remains consist of domestic cooking and storage vessels of various sizes, with rounded bodies and flanged rims, made using slow-wheel technology, alongside a small quantity of handmade vessels. The forms, fabrics, and incised decorations of the vessels are typical of the late medieval period in the area. The size of the pottery fragments and their degree of

rounding are consistent with samples taken from contemporary open fields in the area that have been under plough (Fernández Fernández, 2017a).

Under the agrarian soils, we have identified a thirteenth-century timber building. The study of early medieval timber buildings in Spain has benefited mainly from the results of rescue archaeology in recent decades, as well as from some academic projects. However, research on later medieval houses, particularly rural and peasant dwellings, has lagged behind. In Asturias, as in some other regions, there is virtually no archaeological evidence of early or late medieval rural vernacular architecture. This excavation allowed for the recovery of the complete floor plan of a timber peasant house dated to the thirteenth century. The rectangular structure consisted of twenty postholes outlining an area of around 33 square metres, containing refuse pits and hearths. We also recovered abundant animal bones and other environmental evidence from the site. The house is extremely simple in structure and layout, and the associated artefacts are equally simple and sparse; this contrasts markedly with many contemporary buildings excavated in other parts of Europe.

Fig. Medieval archaeological features and reconstruction of a XIII ct. house.

Stone was in widespread use for peasant houses in Italy from the twelfth century, and in England and Wales a century later. The findings of our excavation indicate that Asturias lagged behind in this respect: stone buildings and other evidence (such as the use of coins and pottery found in market sites) appear gradually from the fourteenth century onwards. At this point in time, we observe

an intensification of agricultural activity, a growing frequency of coin finds, and the presence of non-local pottery. Our research on this house and its surroundings offers valuable insights into variations in the archaeological record of high medieval peasant houses in Europe (Fernández and Moshenska, 2023).

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Annex

Full text transcription of the IX ct. donation to Santo Adriano de Tuñón by:
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